

A A CORNER CASE IN THE COMPUTATION OF THE FRENCH HOUSING BENEFITS

The computation formulae for the housing benefits are so complex that the government edits each year a [primer about the computation elements](#), that collects the rules scattered in the various regulations and presents them in a concise and logical order.

First and second, we propose a translation of the excerpts of this primer related to the APL and ALS computations in the specific corner case related in Section ?? we want to tackle: an elderly couple (within the meaning of 3° of article D842-16), with one individual earning the minimum wage and the other having no income, which brings their resources to 15,000 € per year. They live in communal housing (“logement-foyer”) that meets the criteria for the 1° of D832-25 , in Zone III, and pay a monthly rent of 360 €.

Third and fourth, we highlight how those rules apply by explaining each step of the computation of the APL and ALS on our corner case; The computations for this corner cases have been checked both manually by the authors and automatically by running our Catala program for the housing benefits computation.

In this example, it is preferable for the household to receive the ALF/ALS rather than the APL. Over one year, this represents a difference of about 120 €, a considerable amount for a low-income household. However, since they are eligible to the APL, that is the allowance they will receive from the CNAF, regardless of the real nature of their situation and needs.

A.1 A Primer on the ALS Computation

The computation of social housing allowance (ALS) is determined according to the formula set out in Article D842-15 of the Construction and Housing Code:

$$ALS = K \times (L + C - L0)$$

The application of this formula implies the prior determination of several variables.

The takeover coefficient “K”. Within the framework of the computation of personal housing aid, in the case of communal housing, this computation is based on the formula set out in the 2° paragraph of article D832-25 of the same code which reads as follows:

$$K = 0.90 - \frac{R}{cm \times N}$$

Where:

- “R” represents the resources of the potential beneficiary.
- “cm” is a multiplying coefficient whose value is set out in Article 30 of the decree of September 27, 2019.
- “N” is the number of units that depends on the number of dependent persons determined according to a scale introduced in d) of 2° of Article D832-25.

K is rounded down to the second decimal.

The rent equivalence “L”. It depends on the family composition according to the figures set out in Article 43 of the decree of September 27, 2019.

The lump sum for charges “C”. It is defined by Article 30 of the decree of September 27, 2019.

The minimum rent “L0”, the computation of which is based on the the minimum equivalence “E0” set out in paragraph 2° of Article D832-26. It is necessary to clarify here the different brackets and rates used in the subsequent computations modes. Indeed, two different sets of brackets and rates are possible in the context of residential accommodation. However, the article detailing the ranges does not mention those used in the second computation mode (the one we are interested in here). The [primer about the computation elements](#) of the APL drawn up by the Ministry of Housing in September 2021 nonetheless includes these values, which we have decided to use in our computation. This source does not have full legal value, but it was confirmed to us by an email from the DGLAN/DHUP/FE4 office on May 25, 2022, that these were the correct values.

L0 is determined by the sum of the rates applied to the brackets resulting from the multiplication of the brackets’ limits by the number of portions “N”, then increased by the product of a lump sum defined in paragraph II of article 31 of the decree of September 27, 2019 and the number of portions “N”, the whole divided by 12. As the wording of this formula is complex, we’ve included here the corresponding Catala code for reference:

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_____ construction_code_regulations.catala_en _____
```catala
scope ComputationPersonalizedHousingBenefitCommunalHousing:
 definition brackets_income_d832_26_multiplied equals
 apply for bracket dans brackets_income_d832_26 of
 IncomeBracket {
 -- high: (match bracket.high with pattern
 -- Infinite: Infinite
 -- Income of bracket_high:
 Income content (bracket_high * n_number_parts_d832_25))
 -- low: bracket.low * n_number_parts_d832_25
 -- rate: bracket.rate
 }
 definition minimal_rent_equivalence equals
 (((sum money for bracket in brackets_income_d832_26_multiplied of
 (if rounded_household_income <= bracket.low
 then 0€
 else
 (match bracket.high with pattern
 -- Income of bracket_high:
 (if rounded_household_income >= bracket_high
 then
 (bracket_high - bracket.low) * bracket.rate
 else
 ((rounded_household_income - bracket.low) * bracket.rate))
 -- Infinite:
 (rounded_household_income - bracket.low) * bracket.rate)
))) +
 fixed_amount_d832_26 * n_number_parts_d832_25) * (1,0 / 12,0)
```

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Final steps. A lump sum of 5 € should then be deducted from this result and it should be ensured that the minimal expenditure does not need to be subtracted. Then apply the social contribution tax (CRDS¹) rate, round down to the lowest euro and add the CRDS amount again.

A.2 A Primer on the APL Computation

The formula used, in the case of communal housing, is set by article D832-24 of the Construction and Housing Code:

$$\text{APL} = K \times (E - E0)$$

The application of this formula implies the prior determination of several variables.

The takeover coefficient “K”. It is defined in Article D832-24 of the Construction and Housing Code:

$$K = 0.95 - \frac{R - r \times N}{\text{cm} \times N}$$

Where:

- “R” represents the resources of the potential beneficiary.
- “r” is a coefficient set out in Article 30 of the decree of September 27, 2019.
- “cm” is a multiplying coefficient whose value is set out in Article 30 of the decree of September 27, 2019.
- “N” is the number of units that depends on the number of dependent persons determined according to a scale introduced in e) of 1° of Article D832-25.

K is rounded down to the second decimal.

The eligible equivalence of rent and rental charges ceiling “E”. It is set by article 27 of the decree of September 27, 2019.

The computation of the minimum rent and service charge equivalence “E0”. is determined in Article D832-26: it is the sum of rates applied to the brackets resulting from the multiplication of the ranges, listed in article 31, I) of the decree of September 27, 2019, by the number of portions “N”, then increased by the product of a lump sum defined in paragraph II of article 31 of the decree of September 27, 2019 and the number of portions “N”, the whole divided by 12. It is the same formula as in the computation of the ALS presented in Section A.1, but with a different set of brackets and rates.

Final steps. A lump sum of 5 € should then be deducted from this result and it should be ensured that the minimum expenditure does not need to be subtracted. Then apply the CRDS rate, round down to the nearest euro and add the CRDS amount again.

¹The contribution for the reimbursement of the social debt (CRDS) is a tax created by decree n° 96-50 of January 24, 1996, relative to the reimbursement of the social debt.

A.3 ALS Computation for Our Corner Case

$$ALS = K \times (L + C - L_0)$$

Where:

- $K = 0.90 - \frac{R}{cm \times N} = 0.90 - \frac{15000}{1.5 \times 21420.91} = 0,43$
- $L = 320.73\text{€}$
- $C = 54.22\text{€}$

For L_0 , it is first necessary to multiply the ranges by the number of portions N , which in this case is 1.5, to obtain the brackets, before applying the rates. This yields :

- 0% between 0€ and $1423.03 \times 1.5 = 2134.54\text{€}$
- 2.40% between 2134,54€ and $2047.61 \times 1.5 = 3071.42\text{€}$
- 20,80% between 3071,42€ and $2629.85 \times 1.5 = 3944.78\text{€}$
- 23,30% between 3944,78€ and $4095.05 \times 1,5 = 6142.58\text{€}$
- 32,80% between 6142,58€ and 15000€.

Hence,

$$L_0 = \frac{3619.29 + 76.32}{12} = 307.97\text{€}$$

Therefore:

$$ALS = 0.43 \times (320.73 + 54.22 - 307.97) = 28.80\text{€}$$

After applying the lump sums and the CRDS, we obtain:

$$ALS = 23.12\text{€}$$

A.4 APL computation for Our Corner Case

$$APL = K \times (E - E_0)$$

Where:

- $K = 0.95 - \frac{R-r \times N}{cm \times N} = 0.95 - \frac{15000 - 1217.26 \times 1.8}{13393.40 \times 1.8} = 0,41$
- $E = 360\text{€}$ (the rent is below the rent limit in our corner case)

For E_0 , it is first necessary to multiply the tiers by the number of portions N , which in this case is 1.8, to obtain the brackets, before applying the percentages. This gives:

- 4% between 0€ and $1948.10 \times 1.8 = 3056.58\text{€}$
- 10,40% between 3056,58€ and $2678.71 \times 1.8 = 4821.68\text{€}$
- 21,60% between 4821,68€ and $3896.18 \times 1.8 = 7013.12\text{€}$
- 26,40% between 7013,12€ and $5357.44 \times 1.8 = 9643.39\text{€}$

- 32% between 9643,39€ and $6331.29 \times 1.8 = 11396.32\text{€}$
- 48% between 11396,32€ and 15000€

Hence:

$$E0 = \frac{3735.48 + 45.57 \times 1.8}{12} = 318.13\text{€}$$

Therefore:

$$\text{APL} = 0.41 \times (360 - 318.13) = 17.17\text{€}$$

After applying the lump sums and the CRDS, we obtain :

$$\text{APL} = 12.06\text{€}$$